

THE IMPORTANCE OF PSYCHOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE IN TEACHER'S ACTIVITY

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of pedagogical-psychological knowledge and skills in the work of pedagogues.

Key words: Educational system, teacher-pedagogue, psychology, ability, skill.

Indeed, the role of education is extremely important in achieving happiness and pure human activity in human life. It is known that the positive result for each of us is the product of our work if we can form the spirit of loyalty to our national customs, traditions, and our indelible heritage, which are dear to us in the education of young people. For this, first of all, we need to inculcate concepts such as national pride, national consciousness, national idea, spirituality, and high culture into the minds of young people. Because without knowing and studying history, without taking mental and spiritual nourishment from it, the future, future dreams and hopes cannot be achieved.

It is important for the teacher to know that the purpose of education changes depending on the requirements of society and the age characteristics of students, to take into account the components of education and the connections between them. When it comes to teaching and educating the young generation in the process of implementing the continuous education system, such an extremely complex and multifaceted task can be carried out only by teaching staff with high qualifications and pedagogical skills. It should be noted that it can be increased. Therefore, teaching is a great art. One or another pedagogue cannot easily achieve this art by himself. Therefore, he has great passion and enthusiasm for the teaching profession, that is, to become a real trainer for a healthy generation, who quickly and deeply understands the demands of the times, and consistently implements his scientific, socio-political level, and pedagogical skills. can only be achieved by those who are progressive, well armed with the idea and ideology of independence, true patriots and hardworking people. A teacher is considered a person with special pedagogical, psychological and specialist knowledge and methodical training, as well as high moral qualities.

The system of skills necessary for the effective pedagogical activity of teachers: knowledge, ability to understand the child, observation, speech skills, organization, ability to see the future, distribution of attention, correct

assessment of the situation, emergence timely elimination of all kinds of possible conflicts, making students interested in learning. It is carried out by the future teachers regularly performing the following tasks:

1. Future teachers will be equipped with the theoretical and methodological foundations of pedagogical skills.
2. Future teachers will develop the need and desire to independently master the secrets of pedagogical skills reflected in our national customs and traditions and the rich creative heritage of Central Asian thinkers.
3. Based on the acquired pedagogical-psychological and methodical knowledge, skills and qualifications, each future teacher forms his personal pedagogical skills.
4. They regularly master the theoretical and practical foundations of organizing and managing the educational process based on the latest modern methods and forms typical of world standards.
5. In order to improve their professional skills, teachers acquire forms, methods and means of personal-creative skill development.
6. Teachers continuously learn information about the nature, function, and structure of the teacher's skills.
7. They form their professional skills based on the free use of modern information technologies and the portal system. Regardless of what you choose, the research will demonstrate the pedagogical model or teacher's strategy.

The qualities and skills of the teacher are the main determinant of student learning. "Teacher quality is the single greatest factor in explaining student achievement, more so than audience-related issues, such as resources, curriculum guiding principles and assessment methods, or the broader school learning environment, such as schools. in culture and organization".

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